

D. A. Shastitko, L. V. Gusarova, T. A. Zhuravleva

Organization of control in public procurement

KEYWORDS

public procurement,
organization of control,
suppliers,
contracts

Word Cloud Generated by:
<https://wordscloud.pythonanywhere.com/>

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The topic is relevant because transparent and efficient procurement procedures contribute to developing a competitive environment, which positively impacts the economy as a whole. Organization of control contributes to improving the quality of purchased goods and services, which affects citizens' living standards and government agencies' efficiency.

The article aims to identify vulnerabilities in existing control systems and propose measures to eliminate them.

Materials and methods. Scientific articles and legislative and regulatory acts were used as materials. Research methods were document analysis, comparative analysis, and statistical analysis.

Results. The structure of concluded contracts on determining the supplier within the framework of Federal Law 44-FZ in 2022 is considered. Most contracts were concluded through electronic auctions (over 62%) and purchases from a single supplier (28.4%). The structure of concluded agreements on determining a supplier under Federal Law No. 223-FZ in 2022 was also considered. The dynamics of purchases made under Law No. 44-FZ and Law No. 223-FZ in 2020-2022 are presented.

Conclusion. Control in procurement is necessary for the public and municipal procurement system to function normally.

Including sustainable development and social responsibility criteria in public procurement processes may become necessary for future research and practice. In particular, increasing the role of NGOs and civic initiatives in monitoring public procurement can increase transparency and accountability.

Shastitko, D. A., Gusarova, L. V., & Zhuravleva, T. A. (2023). Organization of control in public procurement. *Economic consultant*, (3), 64–75. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2023.3.6>

FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

The topic is relevant because transparent and efficient procurement procedures contribute to the development of a competitive environment, which has a positive impact on the economy as a whole. Notably, control over public procurement ensures the rational and targeted use of budget funds, which is especially important in conditions of limited resources. Organizing control contributes to improving the quality of purchased goods and services, which affects citizens' living standards and government agencies' efficiency.

Organizing control in public procurement is an important aspect of ensuring transparency, efficiency, and accountability in government agencies' work, making this topic relevant for research and practical application.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used were scientific articles and studies from peer-reviewed scientific journals on economics, law and management: Applied Health Economics and Health Policy, Environment Systems and Decisions, SN Business & Economics, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, Applied Network Science, Studies in Computational Intelligence, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Empirical Economics and others.

Legislative and regulatory acts (federal laws regulating public procurement, government resolutions, and orders) were also used.

Research methods: document analysis (study of legislative acts, reports, and other documents to identify existing norms and practices), comparative analysis, and statistical analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Effectiveness of public procurement is an important aspect affecting the use of budget funds and the quality of services provided. For example, F. I. Lessambo writes that public procurement aims to provide timely and cost-effective contracts to qualified contractors and suppliers of goods, works, and services to support government and public services by the principles and procedures set out in the rules of public procurement [1].

Effectiveness of public procurement depends on various factors, including transparency of processes, level of competition, quality of control and monitoring, and on modern technologies. E. N. Sochneva et al. believe it essential to understand how we evaluate the effectiveness of public procurement. If the state budget carries out the assessment, the most important thing is to save money. If we consider it from the point of view of public satisfaction with public services, quality criteria should be implemented in public procurement. If we are talking about the state as a whole, criteria for developing a competitive environment and small businesses should be implemented. The author proposes a system of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of public procurement at the level of a government organization [2].

S. Vogler et al. describe the main characteristics of national centralized pharmaceutical procurement systems in six European countries (Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Italy, Norway, and Portugal). The authors point out the advantages of this system – lower purchase prices, a stronger negotiating position of government purchasers, increased transparency and governance, improved equity, and ultimately improved access to medicines [3].

M. Langseth and H. T. Moe study how stakeholders perceive and evaluate the effects of sustainable public procurement. According to the authors, public procurement initiatives are perceived as having cultural effects in addition to innovative, environmental, economic, and social impacts. A better understanding of how effects are determined and improved feedback mechanisms can help government representatives monitor the procurement system and achieve the desired effects [4].

The effectiveness of public procurement in different countries depends on various factors which vary depending on the political, economic and cultural environment.

B. Hou et al. summarize the historical stage of public procurement in China and the type and mechanism of operating the public procurement management. The authors build a stakeholder-based model for evaluating the effectiveness of public procurement, which has six elements: economics, staff quality, technical management assurance, social responsibility, stakeholder assessment, and efficiency assessment [5].

According to C. Wang et al., China's current public procurement policy has three problems: regulation of the efficiency management of the entire process needs to be optimized, regulation of high-level efficiency management needs to be strengthened, and regulation of disclosing information on the effectiveness of the entire process needs to be improved [6].

M. R. Khan et al. assess the main problems of project procurement in government

agricultural development projects in Bangladesh. According to the authors, among the 10 main problems, “lack of competent procurement personnel” was the most significant; based on the interrelationships between the problems, “political influence” was defined as the most influential problem [7].

Notably, fraud in public procurement is a serious problem that negatively impacts the economy, society, and trust in government institutions.

C. D. Smith writes that fraud in procurement is a hidden crime – due to their secretive nature, these crimes are difficult to detect and, therefore, difficult to prevent [8].

M. S. Lyra writes that fraud, corruption, and collusion are the most common types of crimes in public procurement. They lead to significant monetary losses, inefficiency, and misuse of the state treasury. The authors provide a systematic review of the literature on the most up-to-date data-based methods used to detect crimes in public procurement [9; 10].

F. Decarolis and C. Giorgiantonio present an approach to assessing corruption risk in public tenders using standardized tools applied to detailed data on the content of tender applications [11].

Advanced technologies (electronic trading platforms, blockchain, artificial intelligence [12], cloud technologies, etc.) can significantly improve public procurement by increasing efficiency, transparency, and accountability.

A. O. Taoufik and A. Azmani write that innovative digital tools were proven important and effective in ensuring public procurement aimed for citizens [13].

V. V. Borisova et al. consider using digital technologies and logistics tools in public procurement. According to the authors, the electronic format optimizes the costs accompanying trade operations and increases their efficiency by an average of 25-30% [14].

Thus, studying control in public procurement contributes to developing management theory, economics, and public administration. It allows identifying and systematizing the best practices, methods and approaches to control, which can become the basis for further scientific research.

Scientific research is needed to help identify vulnerabilities in existing control systems and propose measures to address them, which is essential for increasing transparency and accountability. Research is relevant to creating new models and control tools that will be more effective in the face of modern challenges such as digitalization and globalization. Research on introducing new technologies (for example, blockchain, AI) into public procurement control is also essential and can lead to significant improvements in this area.

RESULTS

The state and municipal procurement system in the Russian Federation is steadily developing and improving. Electronic document management allows carrying out control activities quickly. Consolidating documents on one electronic resource greatly simplifies collection of necessary information for monitoring activities.

Due to the abundance of legal acts regulating contractual activities, the authorities overseeing this area analyze documents from all stages of procurement. Participants in the contract system must post a procurement schedule promptly, accept and fulfill budgetary and monetary obligations, form the initial maximum contract price, justify the choice of a supplier's identification method, conclude and execute the contract promptly, and perform calculations on it. The centralized procurement information collection system allows the state financial control authorities to promptly identify violations, saving time, personnel, and financial resources for monitoring activities. Thus, development of the unified procurement information system (or unified procurement platform, UPP) contributes to the transparency of public procurement and the efficiency of control measures.

Control can be classified according to various criteria such as subjects of control, rules of implementation, source of information, and form of control. Legislative and executive authorities may exercise control over procurement activities. In addition, internal financial control and audit affect the organization's compliance with current legislation in procurement. The information basis for conducting a control event may consist of documents posted electronically (for example, the UPP contains information about publication dates and the content of documents, which allows verifying their compliance with established requirements) and paper media. Control measures can be carried out at the location of the control object. In this case, the information base is formed on data obtained during visual inspection and control actions by the control authorities. The rules of control depend on whether the State or the population carries out the control.

Subjects of procurement control can also be classified according to several criteria. Legislative and executive authorities carry out control activities. At the same time, the authorities are classified by levels: federal, regional, and municipal. At the federal level, the Accounting Chamber of the Russian Federation acts as the subject of external state financial control, which provides the Federal Assembly with the results of control and auditing activities in public procurement. Control of public procurement by the executive branch is carried out by the Federal Treasury and the Federal Antimonopoly Service (see Table 1). At the regional and municipal levels, control and accounting authorities of subjects and municipalities, territorial bodies of the Federal Treasury, and the Federal Antimonopoly Service.

Table 1

Powers of control bodies in the field of procurement activities

Controlbody	Documents confirming the authority	Authority
Accounts Chamber of the Russian Federation	The Constitution of the Russian Federation; Federal Law No. 41-FZ dated April 5, 2013 [5]; CGA302 [7].	Evaluation of effectiveness and expediency of procurement costs; Prevention of budget violations; Execution of prescriptions and representations; Drawing conclusions and recommendations; Contacting law enforcement and judicial authorities.
Federal Treasury	Budget Code of the Russian Federation [1]; Federal Law No. 44-FZ dated April 5, 2013 [2]; Federal Law No. 223-FZ dated July 18, 2011 [3]; Federal Law No. 275-FZ dated December 29, 2012 [4]; Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated December 1, 2004 No. 703 "On the Federal Treasury" [6].	Treasury Procurement Services; Detection and suppression of violations; Verification of correctness of the NMCC formation, method of supplier selection, compliance with the deadlines for registration and publication of documents, and compliance with procurement regulations (by the provisions of 44-FZ); Contacting law enforcement and judicial authorities.
Federal Antimonopoly Service	Federal Law No. 44-FZ dated April 5, 2013; Federal Law No. 223-FZ dated July 18, 2011; Federal Law No. 275-FZ dated December 29, 2012; Order of the Federal Antimonopoly Service of Russia dated November 2, 2014 No. 75/14 [8].	Maintaining fair competition; Prevention and detection of violations of antimonopoly legislation; Ensuring fulfillment of the state defense order; Contacting law enforcement and judicial authorities.

Source: compiled by the author

According to the forms and the legislation of the Russian Federation, control is divided into preliminary and subsequent [15]. In terms of public procurement, preliminary control is an analysis of the schedules of the institutions being audited, compliance of budget obligations with budget allocation limits, etc. Subsequent control includes aspects such as the analysis of implemented contracts, the quality of work performed and services rendered, and product quality control.

The object of control is all participants in the public procurement system. Control measures aim to ensure compliance by the objects of power with the current procurement legislation regarding procurement planning, determining the initial maximum contract price, reasonableness of a method for deciding a supplier, concluding and executing a contract, and settlements under a government contract.

Customers are required to form procurement schedules, the form requirements established by the Government of the Russian Federation. The schedule plans should contain information about the purchase identification codes, and name and timing each purchase. The initial

maximum contract price (hereinafter referred to as the guaranteed maximum price, GMP) should be determined by one of the following methods: comparable market prices method, regulatory method, tariff method, design and estimate method, and cost method. The choice specifics depend on the method of selecting a supplier and the purchased goods, works, and services. The choice of supplier determining method, in turn, depends on the specifics of the purchased goods. The following methods can be used: tenders (open and closed (in electronic form), auctions (open and closed (in electronic form)), and request for quotations in electronic form. The procedure for concluding and executing a contract also depends on the supplier determining method. When controlling these aspects, the state financial control bodies are guided by Federal Law No. 44-FZ, resolutions of the Government of the Russian Federation, and Orders of the Ministry of Finance of the Russian Federation. The structure of public procurement by supplier identification methods for 2022 is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The structure of concluded contracts for the method of determining the supplier under Federal Law 44-FZ in 2022, in units. [Source: The author compiled this report using data from the Unified Information System in procurement]

According to Figure 1, a large proportion of contracts under Federal Law No. 44-FZ were concluded through electronic auctions (more than 62%) and purchases from a single supplier (28.4%). The shares of other supplier identification methods in the overall structure of concluded contracts are insignificant. Thus, government agencies often use an open auction and purchase from a single supplier to determine the contractor for the contract.

Analysis of data published in the Unified Information System on procurement under Federal Law No. 223-FZ dated July 18, 2011, reveals that purchases from a single supplier predominate, accounting for more than 62% of all purchases (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Structure of contracts concluded by determining the supplier under Federal Law No. 223-FZ in 2022, units. [Source: The author compiled this report using data from the Unified Information System in procurement]

This circumstance is explained by the fact that purchases under Law No. 223-FZ are carried out by organizations at their own expense (unlike 44-FZ, according to which the source of purchase is funds from the relevant budget of the budgetary system of the Russian Federation). In addition, the timing of the procurement procedure from a single supplier is significantly shorter compared to other (competitive) methods for determining the contractor. Another factor is companies such as Roscosmos and Rosatom – they purchase specific types of equipment, including production, quality, and supply, which every supplier cannot provide.

Figure 3 shows the dynamics of purchases made under Law No. 44-FZ and Law No. 223-FZ, which shows that the value of contracts concluded under Law No. 223-FZ was many times higher than that of contracts concluded under Law No. 44-FZ until 2022.

Figure 3. Dynamics of concluded contracts in Law No. 44-FZ and Law No. 223-FZ in 2020-2022, trillion rubles. [Source: The author compiled this report using data from the Unified Information System in procurement]

At the same time, analysis of the number of contracts concluded (see Figure 4) allows us to conclude there are more contracts under Law No. 44-FZ than under 223-FZ.

Figure 4. Dynamics of the number of contracts concluded in the context of Law No. 44-FZ and Law No. 223-FZ in 2020-2022, units. [Source: compiled by the author according to the data of the Unified Information System in procurement]

Control in procurement is a necessary and indispensable condition for normal functioning of the public and municipal procurement system. Direct implementation of substantive aspects of control bodies' activities is regulated by the legal framework in the field of procurement, the high differentiation of which is due to the versatility of procurement activities and to specifics of participants in the public procurement system and of procurement mechanisms for certain goods, works, and services [16]. The effectiveness of control activities in procurement directly depends on the current legislation, therefore, optimizing the regulatory framework is a priority for the development of the public procurement system in the Russian Federation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thus, constant monitoring of changes in the legislation on public procurement will allow timely adaptation of control mechanisms to new requirements.

Notably, introducing modern information technologies such as electronic trading platforms, blockchain and AI can significantly increase transparency and efficiency of control in public procurement [17]. Developing integrated management systems that combine procurement control with other aspects of public administration (for example, financial control) is also relevant.

Research and implementation of new approaches to control (such as a risk-based approach that allows focusing resources on the most vulnerable areas) is necessary.

Including criteria for sustainable development and social responsibility in public procurement s may become an important area for future research and practice. In particular, increasing the role of NGOs and civic initiatives in monitoring public procurement can increase transparency and accountability.

REFERENCES

1. Lessambo, F. I. (2022). Public Procurement: Laws and Regulations. In: *International Project Finance*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-96390-3_5
2. Sochneva, E. N. et al. (2022). Efficiency of Public Procurement in Russia. In: *Silhavy, R. (eds) Cybernetics Perspectives in Systems. CSOC 2022. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 503. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-09073-8_40
3. Vogler, S., Bauer, E. & Habimana, K. (2022). Centralised Pharmaceutical Procurement: Learnings from Six European Countries. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*, 20, 637–650. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-022-00729-w>
4. Langseth, M., & Moe, H. T. (2022). Driving through dense fog: a study of the effects and control of sustainable public procurement of electric cars. *Environment Systems and Decisions*, 42, 572–585. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-022-09854-2>
5. Hou, B., Chai, Y., & Xiao, X. (2021). The Study of the Mode and Operation Mechanism of Government Procurement Management in China. In: *Liu, S., Boh6cs, G., Shi, X., Shang, X., Huang, A. (eds) LISS 2020*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-4359-7_13
6. Wang, C., Cao, F. & Yang, J. (2021). Whole-process performance management of government procurement: a quantitative analysis of 58 policy texts. *SN Business & Economics*, 1, 163. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43546-021-00168-0>
7. Khan, M. R., Tabassum, N., & Khan, N. A. et al. (2022). Procurement challenges in public-sector agricultural development projects in Bangladesh. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9, 447. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01468-y>
8. Smith, C. D. (2022). Detecting and Preventing Public Procurement Fraud. In: *White-Collar Crime and the Public Sector*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-12567-6_7
9. Lyra, M. S., Dam6sio, B., & Pinheiro, F. L. et al. (2022). Fraud, corruption, and collusion in public procurement activities, a systematic literature review on data-driven methods.

- Applied Network Science*, 7, 83. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41109-022-00523-6>
10. Lyra, M. S., Pinheiro, F. L., & Bacao, F. (2022). Public Procurement Fraud Detection: A Review Using Network Analysis. In: *Benito, R. M., Cherifi, C., Cherifi, H., Moro, E., Rocha, L. M., Sales-Pardo, M. (eds) Complex Networks & Their Applications X. COMPLEX NETWORKS 2021*. Studies in Computational Intelligence, vol. 1072. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93409-5_11
 11. Decarolis, F., & Giorgiantonio, C. (2022). Corruption red flags in public procurement: new evidence from Italian calls for tenders. *EPJ Data Science*, 11, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjds/s13688-022-00325-x>
 12. Niyazbekova, S. U., Kurmankulova, R. Z., Anzorova, S. P., Goigova, M. G., & Yessymkhanova, Z. K. (2021). Digital Transformation of Government Procurement on the Level of State Governance. In: *Popkova, E. G., Ostrovskaya, V. N., Bogoviz, A. V. (eds) Socio-economic Systems: Paradigms for the Future*. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control, vol. 314. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56433-9_69
 13. Taoufik, A. O., & Azmani, A. (2022). Toward a Holistic Public Procurement 4.0. Case Study: Moroccan Public Procurement. In: *Hamlich, M., Bellatreche, L., Siadat, A., Ventura, S. (eds) Smart Applications and Data Analysis. SADASC 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 1677. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20490-6_9
 14. Borisova, V. V., Lysochenko, A. A., Vorobyev, G. A., Pavlenko, I. I., & Avsharov, A. G. (2021). Digital Technologies in Public Procurement Logistics. In: *Popkova, E. G., Sergi, B. S. (eds) Modern Global Economic System: Evolutional Development vs. Revolutionary Leap. ISC 2019. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 198. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69415-9_154
 15. Budget Code of the Russian Federation dated July 31, 1998, No. 145-FZ. Available at: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_19702/68f24d27edee7d0ca5315de64a951b15f0af209f/ (accessed on May 29, 2023)
 16. Federal Law "On the State Defense Order" dated December 29, 2012 No. 275-FZ (latest edition). Available at: https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_140175/ (accessed on May 29, 2023)
 17. Sokolov, I. A., & Filippova, I. N. (2022). Regional Government Expenditure Efficiency Evaluation for Housing and Utilities in Russia. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 33, 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700722040116>
 18. Shooshtarian, S., Maqsood, T., & Wong, P. S. P. et al. (2022). Application of Sustainable Procurement Policy to Improve the Circularity of Construction and Demolition Waste

Resources in Australia. *Materials Circular Economy*, 4, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-022-00069-z>

19. Tu, X., & Shi, D. (2022). Policy Framework on Procurement of SOEs in China. In: Chaisse, J., Gyrski, J., Sejko, D. (eds) Regulation of State-Controlled Enterprises. *International Law and the Global South*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1368-6_28
20. Tas, B. K. O. (2023). Bunching below thresholds to manipulate public procurement. *Empirical Economics*, 64, 303–319. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-022-02250-4>

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Danil A. Shastitko (Russia, Moscow) – Student of the Faculty of Finance. Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation. E-mail: shastitkoda@mail.ru

Lyubov V. Gusarova (Russia, Moscow) – Doctor of Economics, Professor of the Department of Financial Control and Treasury. Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation. E-mail: lvgusarova@fa.ru

Tatiana A. Zhuravleva (Canada, St. John) – Chartered Professional Accountants. Tax Specialist. OSCO Group Services. E-mail: zhuravleva21@gmail.com

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/09/01/shastitko/>

Received: Mar 28, 2023 | **Accepted:** Jun 26, 2023 | **Published:** Sep 1, 2023

Editor: : Tamara K. Rostovskaya, Professor, Dr. Sci. (Sociol.). Russian State Social University, RUSSIA

Copyright: © 2023 Shastitko, D., Gusarova, L., Zhuravleva, T. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.